

Stability constants of some bivalent metal ions with naphthofuran-2-carbohydrazone Schiff base

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The stability constants of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 metal complexes formed between Th^{IV}, UO₂^{II}, Cu^{II}, Pb^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Ba^{II}, Ca^{II} and Mg^{II} metal ions with Schiff bases NHPC, NHMePC, NHMeOPC and NHCIPC were determined by potentiometric titration technique. Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration method as modified by Irving-Rossotti was used to calculate the pK_{HL}^H , $\log K_{ML}^M$ and $\log K_{ML_2}^{ML_2}$ values in 60 : 40% (v/v) alcohol-water medium at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ temperature and at constant ionic strength of 0.1 M NaClO₄. The correlation between $\log K$ values and some of the fundamental properties of the metal ions are discussed. The negative ΔG° values indicate that complex formation is spontaneous one.

In view of the biological importance of the naphthofuran derivatives¹, it was thought worthwhile to study the solution stability of complexes of biologically important metal ions and there is a need for information on stability constants of Schiff base viz. naphtho[2,3-*a*]furan-2-carboxy-[2'-hydroxyphenyl]carbohydrazone (NHPC), naphtho[2,3-*a*]furan-2-carboxy-[2'-hydroxy-5'-methylphenyl]carbohydrazone (NHMePC), naphtho[2,3-*a*]furan-2-carboxy-[2'-hydroxy-5-methoxyphenyl]carbohydrazone (NHMeOPC), and naphtho[2,3-*a*]furan-2-carboxy-[2'-hydroxy-5'-chlorophenyl]carbohydrazone (NHCIPC), derived from the condensation of naphthofuran-2-carbohydrazone² with salicylaldehyde/5-methyl/5-methoxy/5-chlorosalicylaldehyde. The metal ions used were Th^{IV}, UO₂^{II}, Pb^{II}, Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Ba^{II}, Ca^{II} and Mg^{II}. The stability constants were determined by using Calvin-Bjerrum potentiometric pH titration technique in 60 : 40% alcohol-water medium at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ temperature and at constant ionic strength of 0.1 M NaClO₄.

Results and discussion

Proton-ligand stability constants :

In the ligands it is a phenolic group which takes part in the complex formation after release of hydrogen atom. The equilibrium involved may be represented as

Since there is only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during the complex formation. The \bar{n}_A values are calculated and are in the range of $0.210 < \bar{n}_A < 0.68$ for the

reagent of NHPC, NHMePC, NHMeOPC and NHCIPC. This indicates that there is only one proton per ligand molecules. The values of pK_{HL}^H were calculated by, half integral method at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$, graphical method from $\log \bar{n}_A/(1 - \bar{n}_A)$ vs B and pointwise calculation method, $\log \bar{n}_A/(1 - \bar{n}_A) + B = pK_{HL}^H$. There is a good agreement between pK_{HL}^H values obtained by all these methods (Table 1).

In the present investigation the pK_a values of Schiff bases are in order of $\text{CH}_3 > \text{H} > \text{OCH}_3 > \text{Cl}$ is observed. The variation in pK_a values may be explained on the basis of the strength of the hydrogen bond formed between the phenolic hydrogen and nitrogen of azomethine group³. The electron withdrawing group in *para* position to -C=N- in the case of NHCIPC and NHMeOPC weaken the hydrogen bond, thereby facilitating the easy liberation of the phenolic proton in solution, as a results the pK_a values are less than unsubstituted NHPC. The electron releasing group like CH_3 present at *para* position to -OH group strengthening the hydrogen bonding in NHMePC and thereby rendering the dissociation of H^+ ions from phenolic groups more difficulty and this cause the higher pK_a values of NHMePC compared to NHPC.

Metal-ligand stability constants :

The metal titration curves are well separated from acid and ligand titration curves indicating the formation of metal complexes in solution. The \bar{n} values for different ligands are given in Table 2. The \bar{n} value indicate that the formation of both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes in solution. The values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ are calculated by, half integral method, pL vs \bar{n} , at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5, graphical method pL vs $\log \bar{n}$

Table 1. Stability constants of metal complexes with Schiff base ligands at $\mu = 0.1 M$ NaClO₄ and temp. = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ C$

Ligands	Stepwise stability constants	Th ^{IV}	UO ₂ ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Pb ^{II}	Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Cd ^{II}	Ba ^{II}	Ca ^{II}	Mg ^{II}
NHPC pK = 9.59	log k_1	9.384	9.288	9.242	6.983	6.782	6.583	6.583	5.068	4.094	3.980	4.369
	log k_2	8.841	–	–	4.789	4.869	4.648	4.648	4.442	–	–	–
	log β_2	18.225	9.288	9.242	11.763	11.847	11.231	11.231	9.511	4.094	3.980	4.369
	– ΔG°	25.270	12.878	12.814	16.310	16.427	15.573	15.573	13.187	5.677	5.519	6.059
NHMePC pK = 9.87	log k_1	10.60	9.555	9.412	6.557	6.335	5.861	7.382	5.733	–	–	4.275
	log k_2	9.219	8.551	–	–	4.828	–	5.725	4.809	–	–	–
	log β_2	19.819	18.106	9.412	6.557	11.162	5.861	13.107	10.542	–	–	4.275
	– ΔG°	27.479	25.105	13.05	9.092	15.476	8.127	18.174	14.617	–	–	5.928
NHMeOPC pK = 9.11	log k_1	8.745	7.58	7.012	6.349	6.438	6.456	6.068	5.161	3.975	3.875	4.232
	log k_2	8.225	5.251	–	–	4.539	4.462	4.334	4.401	–	–	–
	log β_2	16.965	12.831	7.012	6.349	10.977	10.918	10.402	9.562	3.975	3.875	4.217
	– ΔG°	23.522	17.791	9.722	8.804	15.229	15.139	14.423	13.258	5.512	5.373	5.847
NHCIPC pK = 8.842	log k_1	8.945	7.470	5.886	6.227	4.412	4.246	5.158	4.514	3.973	–	3.882
	log k_2	8.021	5.085	4.528	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
	log β_2	16.966	12.555	10.414	6.227	4.412	4.246	5.158	4.514	3.973	–	3.882
	– ΔG°	23.524	17.408	14.439	8.634	6.117	5.887	7.152	6.258	5.509	–	5.383

– ΔG° values are in kcal/mol.

Table 2. Stability constants of metal complexes for different ligands

Ligands	Metal ions	\bar{n}	Metal ions	\bar{n}
NHPC	Cu ^{II}	0.040 < \bar{n} < 1.819	Ba ^{II}	0.245 < \bar{n} < 0.764
	Co ^{II}	0.301 < \bar{n} < 1.888	Ca ^{II}	0.085 < \bar{n} < 0.728
	Ni ^{II}	0.291 < \bar{n} < 1.888	Pb ^{II}	0.291 < \bar{n} < 1.886
	Cd ^{II}	0.143 < \bar{n} < 1.761	Th ^{IV}	1.363 < \bar{n} < 1.683
	Zn ^{II}	0.050 < \bar{n} < 1.819	UO ₂ ^{II}	1.034 < \bar{n} < 1.873
	Mg ^{II}	0.107 < \bar{n} < 0.862		
NHMePC	Cu ^{II}	0.379 < \bar{n} < 0.631	Pb ^{II}	0.105 < \bar{n} < 0.596
	Co ^{II}	0.200 < \bar{n} < 1.735	Zn ^{II}	0.085 < \bar{n} < 1.762
	Ni ^{II}	0.161 < \bar{n} < 0.759	Th ^{IV}	1.363 < \bar{n} < 1.883
	Cd ^{II}	0.040 < \bar{n} < 1.550	UO ₂ ^{II}	1.362 < \bar{n} < 1.903
	Mg ^{II}	0.245 < \bar{n} < 0.699		
NHMeOPC	Cu ^{II}	0.294 < \bar{n} < 0.741	Ba ^{II}	0.143 < \bar{n} < 0.648
	Co ^{II}	0.120 < \bar{n} < 1.754	Ca ^{II}	0.089 < \bar{n} < 0.729
	Ni ^{II}	0.130 < \bar{n} < 1.642	Pb ^{II}	0.240 < \bar{n} < 0.563
	Cd ^{II}	0.214 < \bar{n} < 1.700	Th ^{IV}	1.322 < \bar{n} < 1.562
	Zn ^{II}	0.060 < \bar{n} < 1.781	UO ₂ ^{II}	1.248 < \bar{n} < 1.801
	Mg ^{II}	0.078 < \bar{n} < 0.935		
NHCIPC	Cu ^{II}	0.271 < \bar{n} < 1.806	Ba ^{II}	0.183 < \bar{n} < 0.739
	Co ^{II}	0.142 < \bar{n} < 0.724	Pb ^{II}	0.371 < \bar{n} < 0.627
	Ni ^{II}	0.175 < \bar{n} < 0.830	Th ^{IV}	1.293 < \bar{n} < 1.584
	Cd ^{II}	0.087 < \bar{n} < 0.936	UO ₂ ^{II}	0.100 < \bar{n} < 1.759
	Zn ^{II}	0.152 < \bar{n} < 0.619	Mg ^{II}	0.131 < \bar{n} < 0.706

($1 - \bar{n}$) and pL vs $\log \tau(2 - \bar{n})/(\bar{n} - 1)$ and calculation method $\log K_{ML}^M = pL + \log \bar{n}/(1 - \bar{n})$ and $K_{ML_2}^M = pL + \log \tau(2 - \bar{n})/(\bar{n} - 1)$. The values obtained by all these methods are in good agreement (Table 1).

In the present study, we observe the $\log K_1 > \log K_2$. This may be due to interaction of second ligand molecules is weaker than the first one⁴. In the present study, we observe the stability order for different ligands and metal ions as : NHPC, Th > UO₂ > Cu > Ni > Pb > Co > Zn > Cd > Mg > Ba > Ca; NHMePC, Th > UO₂ > Cu > Pb > Zn > Co > Ni > Cd > Mg; NHMeOPC, Th > UO₂ > Cu > Ni > Co > Pb > Zn > Cd > Mg > Ba > Ca; NHCIPC, Th > UO₂ > Pb > Cu > Zn > Cd > Co > Ni > Ba > Mg.

These orders are in good agreement and in accordance with Irving-William's order⁵. The negative ΔG° values indicate the reactions are spontaneous one.

Correlation between $\log K_{ML}^M$ values with some properties of central metal ions : The direct correlation of stability of metal complexes with ligand basicity is shown by comparing the stability per unit base strength i.e. $\log \beta/\Sigma pK$. The ratio of all the metals are approximately same except Th^{IV}, UO₂^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes, Th^{IV} and UO₂^{II} are radio active elements which are significantly larger. The higher values of copper complex indicate the extensive π -interactions.

The graph of $\log K_{ML}^M$ vs atomic number shows that there is a monotonic rise to maximum of Cu^{II} followed by lower value of Zn^{II} . This trend shows that stability seems to decrease with basicity of metal ion i.e. weakly basic metals like Cu^{II} forms strong chelate. In the case of $\log K_{ML}^M$ vs electronegativity of the metal ions, it is observed that stability increases as electronegativity of the metal ions increases except Co^{II} which suggest that metal-ligand bond would be a covalent one.

Experimental

Preparation of Schiff base :

The Schiff bases were prepared by using the following general methods. The equimolar quantity of naphthofuran-2-carbohydrazide (0.1 M) in alcohol (25 mL) and salicylaldehyde/5-methyl/5-methoxy/5-chlorosalicylaldehyde (0.1 M) in (10 mL) alcohol were mixed and the reaction mixture was refluxed on water bath for about 5 h. On partial removal of the solvent (50%) by evaporation and cooling the reaction mixture to room temperature, light yellowish crystalline Schiff bases separated, was collected by filtration, washed with alcohol and recrystallized from alcohol. The purity of the Schiff bases were checked by TLC. The physical data of the Schiff bases are given as follows,

Ligands	Mol. formula	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)
NHPC	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$	261	85
NHMePC	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$	240	80
NHMeOPC	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$	165	85
NHCIPC	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$	285	75

IR spectra : KBr pellets, $\nu(\text{N-H}) = 3430\text{--}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu(\text{C=O}) = 1680\text{--}1750\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu(\text{C=N}) = 1624\text{--}1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\nu(\text{O-H}) = 3600\text{--}3360\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

R = CH_3 , H, OCH_3 or Cl

Preparation of solutions : The standard solution of Schiff base (0.002 M) was prepared in absolute alcohol by

dissolving requisite quantity of the Schiff base just before use. The stock solutions of NaClO_4 (1 M), HClO_4 (0.01 M), metal ion solution (0.002 M) and NaOH (0.101 M) were prepared as per reported earlier⁶.

pH-meter and accessories :

All titration were carried out with an Elico LI-127 pH-meter and was calibrated with the standard buffers (pH 4.0 and 9.18). The experiments were carried out in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen. The pH values (pH-meter readings) in non-aqueous solution were corrected as per literature⁷. All titrations were carried out in doubled walled glass at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$. It is observed that there is no hydrolysis of ligand under present experimental conditions as evidence by no change in pH values of the solution with time. The experimental procedure involves the three sets of titration are acid titration, ligand titration and metal titrations. These three sets were titrated independently against standard (0.101 M) NaOH solution and at (0.1 M) ionic strength of NaClO_4 . All titrations were carried out in 60 : 40% (v/v) alcohol-water medium and the experiments were repeated twice to get the reproducible values.

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